

Physico-Chemical Properties of Candy Developed With Pulp of Wild Fruits From The Gadchiroli Forest of Maharashtra State

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Abstract

Underutilized wild fruits serve as a remarkable source of vitamins and minerals such as calcium, phosphorus, iron and many other constituents. The study was employed for preparation of wild fruit pulp candy and evaluate the physico-chemical properties. The pulp of five wild fruits was found suitable after using pectin test, hence were selected for the experiment and evaluation of physico-chemical properties of developed candy observed high moisture, and ash content as compare to control fruit candy. Total sugar content of experimental candies was significantly lower than control candy. Jamun (*Syzygiumcumini*), Ber (*Ziziphus mauritiana*), Karonda (*Carissa carandas*), Aaola (*Phyllanthus emblica*) and Tamarind (*Tamarindus indica*) was naturally rich in vitamins and minerals. These fruits can be preserved in the form of candies for future use and become sustainable source for nutritional security.

Keywords

Wild Fruits, Physico Chemical Properties, Candy, Gadchiroli Forest.

Introduction

Fruits serve as an important and essential source of vitamins and minerals such as Calcium, Phosphorus, Iron and many other constituents (Vengaiiah et al., 2021). In India, less than 2% of fruits are processed against 65% in the United States. Therefore, there is a great scope to develop skills of local and forest dwelling communities for processing & value addition to the underutilized wild fruits into various products like Jam, Jelly, Fruit Bar and Fruit toffee (Bhanot et al., 2019). In general, candies are prepared by cooking sugars and adding food colouring, flavouring, and acidulants. They may also contain other substances allowed by the legislation, which are characteristic for each type of candy. Chewable candy differs from hard candy, and its formulation employs fat, lower cooking temperatures, and higher percentages of moisture. (Das et al., 2024).

Objective of study

1. To explore the wild fruits suitable for preparation of candy.
2. To analyze physical properties of candies developed with wild fruit pulp.
3. To analyze chemical properties of candies developed with wild fruit pulp
4. To assess the acceptability of the developed candies in masses.

Review of Literature

There are few studies related to the insertion of fruit pulps, especially native fruits, in the formulation of chewable candies. Native fruits have potentially bioactive compounds (Ngurthankhumi et al., 2024), such as phenolic and carotenoid, which contribute to their antioxidant capacity and colour (Meena et al., 2022). In view of the above, select physico-chemical properties of the candy prepared with the pulp of some fruits that are native to the Gadchiroli forest range of Maharashtra State were assessed. The increasing demand for innovative and nutritious food products has driven the exploration of underutilized wild fruits, which are often rich in essential vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants (Semwal et al., 2022). In the Gadchiroli District, forests harbour a diverse range of wild fruits that have been traditionally consumed by local communities but remain largely untapped for commercial food applications. Developing value-added products, such as candies, from these wild fruit pulps could not only enhance their economic potential but also contribute to food security and nutritional diversification.

Physico-chemical evaluation of candy developed with the pulp of wild fruits involves analysing various properties like moisture content, pH, total soluble solids (TSS), total sugar, crude protein, crude fat, crude fiber, ash content, titratable acidity, ascorbic acid, and mineral content (Na and K) (Patra and Basak, 2020). Post-harvest losses of fruits are more serious in developing country like India and total losses from harvest to consumer point are as high as 30-40%, which is worth of thousands of crore rupees (Sishu et al., 2023). In Indian forests, there occur a wide variety of fruits. According to FAO, now, India is the second largest manufacturer of fruits in world produce

Methodology

An experiment was carried out at Department of Horticulture, Collage of Agriculture, Sonapur-Gadchiroli. The control and experimental products were prepared with the variations and proportions of wild fruits pulp, sugar with value addition of natural binders and preservatives. The physico chemical properties of experimental candies developed from wild fruit pulps were compared with commercially available fruit candies and termed as control. The experiment research design was employed for the study. The fresh wild fruits were collected from dense forest of Gadchiroli district (latitude 20.184871 and longitude 79.994796) of Eastern Vidarbha Zone, Maharashtra state of India having boundaries of Chhattisgarh and Telangana states.

Selection of seasonal wild fruits were done on the basis of pectin percentage at the stage of maturity. The selection of the fruits was done on the basis of pectin percentage in the fruits which was derived by Alcohol Precipitation Test. Sugar percentage and total soluble solids were also assessed while selection of the fruits. Following fruits were selected, which are Syzygiumcumini (Jamun), Ziziphus mauritiana (Ber), Phyllanthus emblica (Aonla), Carissa carandas (Karonda), and Tamarindus indica (Tamarind). The selected fruits were washed thoroughly with tap water and then surface sterilized with 70% ethanol solution. Preparation of aqueous extract of selected and required natural and chemical permissible additives were made ready for the product development. Prepared candies were analyzed for physicochemical, quantitative and in vitro antioxidant properties. Moisture and ash contents of the candies were determined gravimetrically, while pH and total sugar content was determined using colorimetric method. The data collected during the study were analyzed following standard statistical tools and with the aid of PASW 18.0 software (formerly known as SPSS 18.0). The comparative assessment of the data obtained for the experimental and control candy was carried out by using 't' test procedure.

Result and Discussion

The observed results are described and discussed as follows.

Following five fruits were selected has sufficient amount of pectin which is necessary for preparation of candies. Aonla (Phyllanthus emblica), Ber (Ziziphus mauritiana) Jamun (Syzygiumcumini.L), Karonda (Carissa carandas) and Tamarind (Tamarindus indica) had the pectin in the range of 0.45-1.12 per cent.

Physico-chemical properties of candy developed with pulp of wild fruits

Moisture content (%)

Moisture content in fruits is crucial for various reasons as it has impact on texture, taste, appearance, and shelf life. It influences how the fruit is processed, stored, and even how it perceived by consumers.

Table No 1: Percent Moisture content of Fruit Candy

Fruit Candy	Moisture content (%)		Min	Max	't' value	p
	Mean	±SD				
Jamun	83.2	±1.9	82.6	84.9	85.29	<0.01
Ber	85.4	±3.2	81.1	88.3	53.7	<0.01
Aonla	82.9	±4.1	80.7	87.3	40.85	<0.01
Karonda	85.9	±0.8	85.2	86.8	175.97	<0.01
Tamarind	22.4	±0.9	22.2	23.5	31.42	<0.01
Control candy	7.2	±0.6	8	5		

Table 1 presents result regarding the moisture content of candies prepared by using wild fruits found in dense forest of Gadchiroli district of Maharashtra. The results show the moisture content of the candy prepared with Jamun was 83.2±1.9% whereas that of Ber was 85.4±3.2%. In addition to above the moisture content of candy prepared with Aonla was 82.9±4.1% and the one prepared with Karonda and Tamarind was 85.9±0.8% and 22.4±0.9% respectively. For control, candy available in the market was used and its moisture content was observed to be only 7.2±0.6%. The moisture content of the control fruit candy and those prepared by using the exotic fruits (obtained from the forest) was compared and the results of this comparison showed that the moisture content of the experimental fruit candies was significantly (p<0.01) high than recorded for the control candy.

pH Level

The pH level of wild fruits is important because it impacts their taste, nutritional value, and how they are processed. It affects acidity, which influences flavor, and also plays a role in the availability of nutrients and the safety of preserving them.

Table No 2: pH level of Fruit Candy

Fruit Candy	pH	Min	Max
Jamun	5.9	5.8	6.1
Ber	4.7	3.5	4.8

Aaonla	3.3	3.01	3.5
Karonda	3.1	2.97	3.12
Tamarind	3.5	3.4	3.8
Control candy	3.8	3.1	4

Table 2 presents result regarding the pH level of candy prepared by using wild fruits found in forest of Gadchiroli district. The results indicated that the pH of the candy prepared with Jamun was 5.9 whereas that of Ber was 4.7. In addition to above the pH of candy prepared with Aaonla was 3.3 and that one's prepared with Karonda and Tamarind was 3.1 and 3.5 respectively. For control, fruitcandy available in the market (Mapro) was used and its pH was observed to be 3.8. The results indicated that the pH level was above 5 in the candies prepared with Jamun.

Total Soluble Solids (mg/L)

Total soluble solids (TSS) is an important quality parameter for wild fruits, primarily because it indicates the fruit's sweetness and influences consumer preference. In wild fruits, TSS levels varies widely and are influenced by factors like genetics, environmental conditions, and fruit maturity.

Table No 3: Total Soluble Solids content level of Fruit Candy

Fruit Candy	Mean	SD	Min	Max	t' value	p
Jamun	13.3	0.8	12.8	14.86	17.9	<0.01
Ber	16.4	2.7	11.9	22.3	15.63	<0.01
Aaonla	68.4	1.2	68.8	68.1	21.47	<0.01
Karonda	5.3	1.9	3.45	8.26	20.41	<0.01
Tamarind	55.8	2.4	42.7	69.9	19.15	<0.01
Control candy	69.5	7.1	66	75		

Table 3 presents results regarding the total soluble solids content of candy prepared by using wild fruits found in forest of Gadchiroli district. The results indicated that the total soluble solids content of the candy prepared with Jamun was 13.3±0.8mg/L whereas that of Ber was 16.4±2.7 mg/L. In addition to above the total soluble solids content of candy prepared with Aaonla was 68.4±1.2 mg/L and that one's prepared with Karonda and Tamarind was 5.3±1.9 mg/L and 55.8±2.4 mg/L respectively. For control a fruit candy available in the market was used and its total soluble solids content was observed to be 69.5±7.1. The total soluble solids content of the control candy and those prepared by using the exotic fruits (obtained from the forest) was compared and the results of this comparison showed that the TSS content of the experimental fruit candies was significantly (p<0.01) high than recorded for the control candy.

Ash content (%)

The ash content of wild fruits is important because it indicates the mineral content, which is crucial for human nutrition. It also provides insights into the fruit's potential for use as food or medicine and can help in understanding its nutritional value and potential health benefits.

Table No 4: Ash content level of Fruit Candy

Fruit Candy	Ash content (%)		Min	Max	t' value	p
	Mean	SD				
Jamun	0.4	±0.09	0.39	0.41	0.45	NS
Ber	1.15	±0.21	1.01	1.3	10.56	<0.01
Aaonla	0.24	±0.06	0.21	0.29	1.24	NS
Karonda	0.52	±0.07	0.4	0.57	8.87	<0.01
Tamarind	1.77	±0.53	1.5	2.7	6.6	<0.01
Control candy	0.2	±0.04	0.1	0.4		

Table 4 presents results regarding the ash content of candy prepared by using wild fruits found from forest of Gadchiroli district. The results indicated that the ash content of the candy prepared with Jamun was 0.4±0.09% whereas that of Ber was 1.15±0.21%. In addition to above the ash content of candy prepared with Aaonla was 0.24±0.06% and that one's prepared with Karonda and Tamarind was 0.52±0.07% and 1.77±0.53% respectively. For control a fruit candy available in the market was used and its ash content was observed to be 0.2±0.04. The ash content of the control candy and those prepared by using the exotic fruits (obtained from the forest) was compared and the results of this comparison showed that the ash content of the experimental fruit candies was significantly (p<0.01) high than recorded for the control candy.

Total Sugar content (%)

The total sugar content in wild fruits is important for both human consumption and ecological functions. From an ecological perspective, sugars are the key energy source for animals that consume fruits, influencing seed dispersal. For humans, sugars are a primary source of energy and influence fruit taste, maturity, and suitability for processing.

Table No 5: Total Sugar content level of Fruit Candy

Fruit Candy	Total Sugar content (%)		Min	Max	t' value	p
	Mean	SD				
Jamun	29.5	±2.5	26.1	36	15.63	NS
Ber	77.3	±3.8	72.3	81.4	0.95	<0.01
Aaonla	46.7	±6.7	28.3	72.6	6.91	<0.01
Karonda	66.9	±3.2	63.4	79.5	2.47	<0.01
Tamarind	33.5	±4.9	28.7	46.2	16.61	<0.01
Control candy	74.3	±5.9	66	85		

Table 5 presents results regarding the total sugar content of candy prepared by using wild fruits found in dense forest of Gadchiroli district. The results indicated that the total sugar content of the candy prepared with Jamun was 29.5±2.5% whereas that of Ber was 77.3±3.8%. In addition to above the total sugar content of candy prepared with Aaonla was 46.7±6.7% and that one's prepared with Karonda and Tamarind was 66.9±3.2% and 33.5±4.9% respectively. For control a candy available in the market was used and its total sugar content was observed to be 74.3±5.9. The total sugar content of the control candy and those prepared by using the exotic fruits (obtained from the forest) was compared and the results of this comparison showed that the total sugar content of the experimental fruit candies was significantly (p<0.01) lower than recorded for the control candy.

Conclusion

The candies prepared from the wild fruits like Karondas, Aaonla, Ber, Jamun and Tamarind were found significantly superior for the physico-chemical properties than the control one. Hence can serve as the potential source for the vitamins and minerals and can be preserved in the form of the candy for future use. The preparation of fruit candy may become the sustainable way to utilisation of underutilised wild fruits for nutritional security. The study demonstrates that traditional forest fruits can be transformed into candies with varying sugar levels, from the exceptionally sweet Ber to the more moderate Tamarind and Jamun. These findings enable targeted product development for different market segments, from traditional sweet-lovers to health-conscious consumers, while maintaining the unique nutritional profiles of these indigenous and neglected fruits.

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